

SYNTHESIS AND STRUCTURE OF 2,3-DIHYDROXYL-5-CARBOXYLBENZENESULFONIC ACID SUPRAMOLECULAR COMPLEX WITH HEXA-AQUA COBALT COMPLEX

Abror Kh.Ruzmetov¹

Aziz B.Ibragimov¹

Jurabek B.Yuldashev²

¹ Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry, Uzbekistan
Academy of Sciences, 100170,

Kh.Abdullaev Str., 77a, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

² Academic Lyceum of the Tashkent Medical Academy, 100109, Shikopar street
3, Almazar district, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

uzchemist@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14506721>

The novel arenesulfonic acid, featuring three functional groups – carboxyl ($-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$), sulfonic acid ($-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$), and hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) – specifically 2,3-dihydroxy-5-carboxybenzenesulfonic acid, was synthesized by Ge et al. in 2018 [1]. The goal of this synthesis was to develop lithium(I)-based metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) with potential applications in areas such as photochemistry, electrochemistry, sensors, catalysis, and especially in gas storage and small molecule separations. The authors successfully obtained two structurally characterized complexes with both discrete and polymeric configurations. However, the exact structure of the ligand itself has not yet been determined. This study focuses on the characterization of the 2,3-dihydroxy-5-carboxybenzenesulfonic acid (anion) structure as part of its supramolecular complex (salt) with the hexaaqua cobalt cation (Fig. 1.).

Figure 1. The molecular structure of the supramolecular compound.

Structural Commentary: The crystal structure of the title compound is composed of three main components: 2,3-dihydroxy-5-carboxybenzenesulfonic acid, a hexaaqua cobalt complex, and an additional water molecule (Fig. 1). Together, these form a supramolecular complex in salt form, where the sulfonic acid fragment (anion) is deprotonated to balance the positive double charge of the cobalt ion (cation). The cobalt ion sits at an inversion center within the P-1 space group of the crystal, leading to three coordinated water molecules in the asymmetric unit. The overall chemical formula of this supramolecular complex is $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6] \cdot 2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_7\text{S}) \cdot 2(\text{H}_2\text{O})$.

The cobalt–oxygen bond lengths are nearly identical, ranging between 2.0810(14) and 2.0924(15) Å. The bond angles around the cobalt ion vary from 94.54(5)° to 85.47(5)°, giving rise to a slightly distorted octahedral geometry around the metal center.

Synthesis method: First, 237 mg (0.1 mmol) of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 10 ml of MCN. Afterward, 46.8 mg (0.2 mmol) of 2,3-dihydroxy-5-carboxybenzenesulfonic acid powder was added to the solution, which was stirred for one hour at 40°C. A clear, light red solution appeared after stirring, which was then transferred to a flat-bottom beaker with small holes to enable slow evaporation at room temperature. After one month, red crystals suitable for X-ray analysis of the compound were obtained with a 48% yield. The crystals were collected, rinsed with acetone, and dried under vacuum.

Elemental analysis: The elemental composition of the compound $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{CoO}_{22}\text{S}_2$ was determined using a Thermo Scientific FlashSmart (CHNS/O) elemental analyzer, following the gas chromatographic separation of combustion gases through a modified Dumas method. The elemental analysis of the compound $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{CoO}_{22}\text{S}_2$ (Mr = 669.4 g/mol) showed the following theoretical and practical values: Theoretical carbon (C) content was 25.1%, while the practical value was 24.617%; for hydrogen (H), the theoretical content was 3.884%, compared to the practical result of 3.684%; sulfur (S) had a theoretical value of 9.56%, with a practical value of 9.263%; and oxygen (O) showed a theoretical content of 52.58%, compared to a practical result of 52.17%.

Aknowledgements: Authors gratefully acknowledge the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation for the financial support (project number F3-20200929348).

References:

Ge, Z.-Y. et al. (2018) "Structure evolution and luminescence properties of lithium(i)-sulfonate complexes constructed from multifunctional

arene-disulfonic acids”, CrystEngComm, 20(21), 2968–2979. doi:
10.1039/C8CE00224J.

